

Comparison of Continuous infusion versus Intermittent Bolus Administration of Epidural Levobupivacaine (0.125%) with Fentanyl for Labour Analgesia: A Comparative Case-Control Study

Gurulingappa I. Herakal^{1,2}, Prashanth Kumar Challangod³, Praveen Kumar Kandakurti⁴,
Prathima Shetty⁵

Author's affiliation

1. Research scholar, Srinivas Institute of Allied Health sciences, Srinivas University
Mangalore, India.
2. Lecturer, College of Health Sciences, Gulf Medical University, Ajman, United Arab
Emirates.
3. Professor and Head of the Department of Anesthesiology and critical care, Srinivas
Institute of Medical Sciences and Research center, Srinivas University, Mangalore,
India.
4. Dean, College of Health Sciences, Gulf Medical University, Ajman, United Arab
Emirates.
5. Assistant Professor, Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology, Nitte (Deemed to
be University), Nitte Institute of Allied Health Sciences (NIAHS), Mangalore, India

*Corresponding Author

Mr. Gurulingappa I. Herakal

1. Lecturer, College of Health Sciences, Gulf Medical University, Ajman, United Arab
Emirates.

Abstract

Introduction: Labor pain requires effective management to enhance maternal comfort and obstetric outcomes. Epidural analgesia, using levobupivacaine with fentanyl, is the gold standard, but optimal delivery regarding continuous epidural infusion (CEI) versus intermittent epidural bolus (IEI) remains debated.

Methodology: This prospective, comparative case-control study at a tertiary hospital compared CEI and IEI in 100 nulliparous women. CEI (n=50) received levobupivacaine 0.125% with fentanyl 2 µg/mL at 8–12 mL/h; IEI (n=50) received a 10 mL bolus with 100 µg fentanyl, then 5–10 mL boluses as needed. Outcomes included VAS pain scores, motor (modified Bromage score) and sensory blockade, maternal vital signs, and fetal heart rate, recorded pre-epidural, every 5 minutes for 15 minutes post-bolus, and hourly until delivery.

Results: Both groups had similar demographics. IEI showed lower VAS scores at 15 minutes, 3 hours, and 5 hours ($p < 0.05$), indicating better pain control and less motor blockade ($p < 0.001$). CEI had denser initial sensory blockade ($p < 0.001$ at 5 and 10 minutes) but similar later levels. CEI showed higher maternal and fetal heart rates ($p < 0.001$), with no non-reassuring fetal patterns.

Conclusion: IEI provides better pain relief and less motor blockade with comparable safety. Further studies should optimize bolus regimens and assess long-term outcomes.

Keywords: levobupivacaine, fentanyl, intermittent epidural bolus, continuous epidural infusion, labor pain

Introduction

Labor pain is among the most severe pain that is experienced by women, often exceeding the intensity of many surgical procedures [1]. The physiological and psychological demands of childbirth necessitate effective pain management to enhance maternal comfort, reduce stress-related complications, and improve overall obstetric outcomes [2]. A range of analgesic techniques, ranging from non-pharmacological methods (breathing exercises and hydrotherapy) to pharmacological options (systemic opioids and regional anaesthesia) were employed [3]. Epidural analgesia is the preferred method for labor pain relief, offering effective, adjustable pain control while supporting maternal mobility and participation in childbirth [4].

Epidural analgesia delivers local anesthetics, often with opioids like fentanyl, to boost effectiveness and duration while reducing side effects [5]. Levobupivacaine, a long-acting local anesthetic, is preferred in obstetrics for its safer profile and lower cardiotoxicity compared to bupivacaine [6,7]. Continuous epidural infusion (CEI) provides steady medication delivery for consistent pain relief but may result in higher total doses, greater motor blockade, and uneven epidural spread [8]. Whereas, intermittent epidural bolus (IEI) techniques, deliver medication in periodic doses, promoting better anesthetic spread, enhanced sensory blockade, and less breakthrough pain [9].

Studies show intermittent bolus techniques in labor analgesia use less local anesthetic, reduce instrumental deliveries, and improve maternal satisfaction by preserving motor function, compared to CEI [10,11]. However, CEI is still favored for its simplicity and consistent pain relief [10-12]. Combining levobupivacaine with fentanyl yields promising results in both techniques, though outcomes vary depending on dosing, patient characteristics, and hospital protocols [13]. Meta-analyses suggest programmed intermittent epidural bolus (PIEB)

provides better pain control during labor's maintenance phase, though outcomes differ by population and anesthetic strength [14].

Despite these advancements, significant research gaps persist, particularly in resource-limited settings like tertiary care hospitals in developing regions, where access to advanced delivery systems such as PIEB pumps may be inconsistent [15]. Limited studies have directly compared CEI and intermittent bolus using levobupivacaine 0.125% with fentanyl in nulliparous women, especially focusing on hemodynamic stability, fetal heart rate variations, and long-term maternal outcomes in the Indian population. This underscores the need for a prospective comparative study to evaluate these techniques, aiming to optimize labor analgesia protocols that balance pain relief with minimal interventions and complications. Hence, the aim of the present study was to compare the potential benefits of continuous infusion and intermittent bolus administration of epidural levobupivacaine 0.125% with fentanyl for labour analgesia.

Materials and Methods

Following approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee with reference number 05/AHS/IEC/2024, a comparative case control study which is a part of the large research project was performed at a tertiary care hospital equipped with facilities for obstetric and anaesthetic care. The study was carried out in the labour and delivery unit, where epidural analgesia is routinely offered to women in labour. The study was performed from March 2024 to July 2025. Moreover, following explanation of the study objectives, procedures, and potential risks in their native language written informed consent was obtained from the patients.

Inclusion criteria

The study included healthy nulliparous women aged 18–45 with a singleton, term (37–42 weeks) fetus in cephalic presentation, American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) class 2, cervical dilation ≤ 5 cm at epidural placement, women in active labour (regular contractions with cervical dilation of at least 3 cm), requesting epidural analgesia for labor pain, no contraindications, and who were willing and able to provide informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

Women who had induced labour, gestational diabetes, a body mass index (BMI) greater than 35 kg/m², hypertensive disorders, or premature rupture of membranes exceeding 18 hours, multiple gestations (e.g., twins or triplets), fetuses with growth retardation or physical abnormalities, or contraindications to epidural analgesia, such as bleeding disorders or infection at the insertion site, women with known allergies to levobupivacaine, fentanyl, or any components of the epidural analgesia solution, women with pre-existing medical conditions that could complicate labour or epidural administration, such as severe heart disease or uncontrolled hypertension, and women unable to communicate effectively or provide feedback on pain levels due to cognitive impairment, or those with unstable labour, including non-reassuring fetal status or other obstetric emergencies.

Sample size determination

The formula used consisted of [16]: $n = (Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta})^2 / \Delta^2 + (Z_{1-\alpha/2})^2 / 2$ where, $\alpha =$ significance level (5%), $\Delta =$ Effect size (0.75), $1 - \beta =$ Power (80%), $n = (1.96 + 0.84)^2 / 0.05^2 + (1.96)^2 / 2 = 33$ participants per group. Accounting for an anticipated dropout rate of 5%, the study included a total of 100 participants consisting of 50 participants per group.

Procedure

All necessary equipment and drugs (levobupivacaine 0.125%, fentanyl) were verified to be available and functional. Demographic data (age, height, weight, BMI, and cervical dilation at the time of epidural insertion), maternal vital signs consisting of heart rate [17], blood pressure [18,19], mean arterial pressure [20], oxygen saturation [21], and respiratory rate [22], along with fetal heart rate [17], were recorded before the epidural, every 5 minutes after the initial bolus for 15 minutes, and then every hour until delivery. Visual analogue scale (VAS) for pain (0-100 mm, 0 mm = no pain and 100 mm = worst pain imaginable) [23,24], motor block as assessed by modified Bromage score [25-27], and sensory dermatome level on the right and left [28-30] were also recorded before the epidural, every 5 minutes after the initial bolus for 15 minutes, and then every hour until delivery. The patients were explained and educated regarding the procedure, potential side effects, and pain assessment methods.

The patients in Group 1 (CEI) were positioned in either the sitting or lateral decubitus position for epidural placement. The insertion site (L3-L4 or L4-L5 interspace) was sterilized with an antiseptic solution and Lidocaine was administered to numb the skin at the insertion site. This was followed by the insertion of an epidural catheter at the L3-L4 or L4-L5 interspace for which correct placement was confirmed by aspiration and a test dose of 3 mL lidocaine with epinephrine. A continuous infusion of levobupivacaine 0.125% with fentanyl 2 µg/mL was started at a rate of 8–12 mL/h, adjusted based on clinical response.

Similarly, the patients in Group 2 (Intermittent bolus administration) were positioned in either the sitting or lateral decubitus position for epidural placement. The insertion site (L3-L4 or L4-L5 interspace) was sterilized with an antiseptic solution and Lidocaine was administered to numb the skin at the insertion site. This was followed by the insertion of an epidural catheter at the L3-L4 or L4-L5 interspace for which correct placement was confirmed by aspiration and a test dose of 3 mL lidocaine with epinephrine. An initial bolus

of 10 mL levobupivacaine 0.125% with 100 µg fentanyl was administered after confirming catheter placement. Epidural analgesia was maintained by administering bolus doses of 5–10 mL levobupivacaine 0.125% with 50–100 µg fentanyl, based on the participant's pain level (assessed via VAS) and cervical dilation.

Statistical analysis:

The data were processed using SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages were used to summarize the collected data. To assess differences in proportions, either the Chi-square test or the Likelihood ratio test was applied. For continuous variables, comparisons between the intermittent epidural bolus (IEI) and CEI groups were conducted using unpaired t-tests.

Results

The IEI and CEI groups were compared for demographic characteristics across several variables, with no statistically significant differences observed. The mean age was 29.42 ± 2.67 years, and 28.94 ± 2.92 years for the IEI group and for the CEI group respectively ($p = 0.393$). Height averaged 161.42 ± 5.65 cm and 162.78 ± 5.75 cm in the IEI group and CEI group respectively ($p = 0.264$). Weight was 65.56 ± 4.35 kg and 64.78 ± 7.90 kg for the IEI group for the CEI group respectively ($p = 0.586$). Body Mass Index (BMI) was 25.20 ± 1.76 kg/m² in the IEI group and 24.45 ± 2.46 kg/m² in the CEI group ($p = 0.112$). Cervical dilation measured 3.18 ± 0.77 cm in the IEI group and 3.12 ± 0.82 cm in the CEI group ($p = 0.708$). All p-values indicated non-significant differences (NS).

Before the administration of epidural anaesthesia, the mean heart rate was 73.33 ± 2.87 bpm in Group IEI and 87.00 ± 2.83 bpm in Group CEI, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.314$, NS). However, significant differences emerged following the initial bolus. At 5 minutes, the heart rate in Group IEI was 73.26 ± 2.95 bpm compared to 87.36 ± 13.48 bpm in Group CEI ($p < 0.001$). This trend continued at 10 minutes (74.76 ± 3.49 vs. 84.54 ± 12.58 bpm, $p < 0.001$), 15 minutes (72.84 ± 3.59 vs. 83.20 ± 11.27 bpm, $p < 0.001$), 1 hour (73.32 ± 3.57 vs. 81.58 ± 11.44 bpm, $p < 0.001$), 2 hours (72.68 ± 4.21 vs. 80.52 ± 10.71 bpm, $p < 0.001$), and 3 hours (76.64 ± 4.91 vs. 81.20 ± 12.19 bpm, $p < 0.001$). At 4 hours post-bolus, the difference was not statistically significant (77.35 ± 4.11 vs. 79.90 ± 11.30 bpm, $p = 0.374$, NS). A significant difference reappeared at 5 hours (73.13 ± 2.50 vs. 83.29 ± 8.77 bpm, $p = 0.014$) and remained significant at 6 hours (74.26 ± 4.52 vs. 86.66 ± 16.17 bpm, $p < 0.001$). These findings indicate that Group CEI consistently exhibited higher heart rates than Group IEI at multiple time intervals following epidural administration, with several of these differences being statistically significant. Figure 1 presents the comparison of patients' average heart rates between the two groups.

Figure 1: Comparison of mean heart rate of patients between the groups

Figure 2 shows the comparison of patients' average systolic blood pressure between the two groups. Before the administration of epidural anaesthesia, the mean SBP was 115.62 ± 7.14 mmHg in Group IEI and 118.44 ± 17.05 mmHg in Group CEI, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.266$, NS). Similarly, at 5 minutes (121.78 ± 8.53 vs. 123.58 ± 12.65 mmHg, $p = 0.439$), 10 minutes (122.26 ± 4.98 vs. 125.22 ± 14.13 mmHg, $p = 0.188$), and 15 minutes (119.12 ± 4.66 vs. 123.44 ± 14.21 mmHg, $p = 0.061$) after the initial bolus, the differences remained statistically non-significant.

However, at 1 hour post-bolus, a statistically significant difference was observed, with Group IEI having a lower SBP (114.38 ± 7.36 mmHg) compared to Group CEI (121.46 ± 10.69 mmHg, $p < 0.001$). This trend continued at 2 hours (116.10 ± 7.65 vs. 120.58 ± 11.93 mmHg,

$p = 0.014$). At 3 and 4 hours post-bolus, the differences were again not significant ($p = 0.201$ and $p = 0.314$, respectively). A significant difference reappeared at 5 hours post-bolus, with Group IEI showing a higher SBP (118.80 ± 6.92 mmHg) compared to Group CEI (109.39 ± 4.01 mmHg, $p = 0.040$). However, by 6 hours, the difference in SBP was no longer significant (118.33 ± 5.66 vs. 111.55 ± 4.32 mmHg, $p = 0.500$). These findings suggest intermittent significant differences in systolic blood pressure between the groups at specific time points following epidural administration.

Figure 2: Comparison of mean systolic blood pressure of patients between the groups

The comparison of mean diastolic blood pressure of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Figure 3. Before epidural anaesthesia, the mean DBP was 73.28 ± 3.85 mmHg in Group IEI and 70.74 ± 11.24 mmHg in Group CEI, with no statistically significant

difference ($p = 0.146$, NS). However, following the initial bolus, significant differences were observed at multiple time intervals. At 5 minutes, the DBP was significantly lower in Group IEI (69.78 ± 2.62 mmHg) compared to Group CEI (73.76 ± 7.70 mmHg, $p = 0.001$), and this trend continued at 10 minutes (70.02 ± 1.87 vs. 73.74 ± 9.89 mmHg, $p = 0.012$), 15 minutes (69.16 ± 4.08 vs. 72.60 ± 9.33 mmHg, $p = 0.015$), and 1 hour (67.16 ± 2.75 vs. 71.24 ± 6.46 mmHg, $p < 0.001$). Statistically significant differences also persisted at 2 hours (68.34 ± 4.53 vs. 71.60 ± 5.71 mmHg, $p = 0.002$), 3 hours (68.74 ± 6.51 vs. 72.28 ± 4.76 mmHg, $p = 0.004$), and 4 hours (67.09 ± 3.01 vs. 71.44 ± 7.02 mmHg, $p = 0.003$) post-bolus.

Interestingly, at 5 hours after the initial bolus, the trend reversed, with Group IEI showing a significantly higher DBP (75.87 ± 4.81 mmHg) compared to Group CEI (65.54 ± 2.32 mmHg, $p < 0.001$). However, by 6 hours, the difference was not statistically significant (76.89 ± 3.89 vs. 67.91 ± 1.30 mmHg, $p = 0.139$, NS). These results indicate significant fluctuations in diastolic blood pressure between the two groups at multiple time intervals following epidural anaesthesia, with Group CEI generally demonstrating higher DBP values in the earlier hours and Group IEI showing elevated DBP at later time points.

Figure 3: Comparison of mean diastolic blood pressure of patients between the groups

The comparison of mean arterial pressure of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Figure 4. Before the administration of epidural anaesthesia, the mean MAP was 74.36 ± 2.05 mmHg in Group IEI and 73.28 ± 10.78 mmHg in Group CEI, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.478$, NS). However, following the initial bolus, significant differences emerged at several time points. At 5 minutes post-bolus, Group CEI showed a higher MAP (78.66 ± 7.69 mmHg) compared to Group IEI (73.58 ± 4.62 mmHg), with the difference being highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Similar significant differences continued at 10 minutes (73.38 ± 2.58 vs. 77.64 ± 8.30 mmHg, $p = 0.001$), 15 minutes (71.94 ± 2.59 vs. 75.34 ± 9.79 mmHg, $p = 0.018$), and 1 hour (70.18 ± 3.90 vs. 76.42 ± 4.94 mmHg, $p < 0.001$). At 2 hours (73.78 ± 4.50 vs. 77.42 ± 5.70 mmHg, $p = 0.001$), 3 hours (73.40 ± 6.13 vs. 77.30 ± 5.82 mmHg, $p = 0.001$), and 4 hours (71.77 ± 2.71 vs. 76.38 ± 5.83 mmHg, $p < 0.001$), the MAP remained significantly higher in Group CEI.

Interestingly, at 5 hours after the initial bolus, Group IEI had a higher MAP (74.27 ± 1.39 mmHg) than Group CEI (71.54 ± 3.42 mmHg), and the difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.045$). A similar significant difference persisted at 6 hours (73.89 ± 1.69 vs. 70.82 ± 2.71 mmHg, $p = 0.049$), again favouring Group IEI. These results highlight significant

fluctuations in mean arterial pressure over time between the two groups, with Group CEI generally exhibiting higher MAP in the initial hours, while Group IEI showed relatively higher values in the later stages.

Figure 4: Comparison of mean arterial pressure of patients between the groups

The comparison of mean respiratory rate of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Figure 5. Prior to the administration of epidural anaesthesia, there was no statistically significant difference in respiratory rate between the two groups (18.92 ± 1.12 breaths/min in Group IEI vs. 18.74 ± 1.55 breaths/min in Group CEI, $p = 0.509$, NS). At 5 minutes after the initial bolus, Group IEI exhibited a significantly lower respiratory rate (18.04 ± 1.11) compared to Group CEI (18.90 ± 1.52), with the difference being statistically significant ($p = 0.003$). However, no significant differences were observed at 10 minutes ($p = 0.242$), 15 minutes ($p = 0.610$), 1 hour ($p = 0.586$), 2 hours ($p = 0.941$), and 3 hours ($p = 0.583$) post-bolus.

Significant differences were again noted at 4 and 5 hours post-bolus. At 4 hours, Group IEI had a lower respiratory rate (17.67 ± 1.60) compared to Group CEI (19.14 ± 1.40), with the difference being highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, at 5 hours, the respiratory rate was

significantly lower in Group IEI (17.87 ± 0.92) compared to Group CEI (19.86 ± 1.41 , $p = 0.019$). However, by 6 hours, the difference was no longer statistically significant (17.89 ± 0.60 vs. 20.45 ± 1.21 , $p = 0.205$, NS). These findings suggest intermittent significant differences in respiratory rate between the two groups at specific time intervals following epidural administration.

Figure 5: Comparison of mean respiratory rate of patients between the groups

The comparison of mean SpO₂ of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Table 1.

Time	Group IEI		Group CEI		p-value (Unpaired t-test)
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
Before epidural anaesthesia	97.12	1.41	97.36	1.19	0.351 NS
5 mins after initial bolus	97.44	0.91	97.38	1.21	0.785 NS
10 mins after initial bolus	96.44	1.50	97.74	0.99	<0.001**
15 mins after initial bolus	97.08	1.61	97.38	1.47	0.295 NS

1 hour after initial bolus	97.98	0.55	98.00	0.81	0.881 NS
2 hours after initial bolus	96.62	1.19	98.06	1.04	<0.001**
3 hours after initial bolus	96.96	1.37	97.44	1.23	0.093 NS
4 hours after initial bolus	97.40	1.33	96.62	1.32	0.005*
5 hours after initial bolus	97.53	0.92	96.82	0.98	0.448 NS
6 hours after initial bolus	98.00	0.87	97.73	0.47	0.998 NS

Table 1: Comparison of mean SpO₂ of patients between the groups

NS- Not significant, * Statistically significant, ** Statistically highly significant

The comparison of mean foetal heart rate of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Table 2.

Time	Group IEI		Group CEI		p-value (Unpaired t-test)
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
Before epidural anaesthesia	137.22	3.77	146.91	3.39	0.090 NS
5 mins after initial bolus	133.16	4.04	153.06	9.21	<0.001**
10 mins after initial bolus	132.48	8.55	154.80	6.95	<0.001**
15 mins after initial bolus	135.08	8.54	156.24	9.25	<0.001**
1 hour after initial bolus	135.62	6.57	151.08	8.41	<0.001**
2 hours after initial bolus	133.62	9.79	152.34	7.82	<0.001**
3 hours after initial bolus	132.70	16.72	149.62	7.62	<0.001**
4 hours after initial bolus	129.49	18.12	138.78	13.18	<0.001**
5 hours after initial bolus	141.53	8.21	141.86	6.91	0.830 NS
6 hours after initial bolus	136.40	6.94	146.48	9.79	<0.001**

Table 2: Comparison of mean foetal heart rate of patients between the groups

NS- Not significant, ** Statistically highly significant

The data for hemodynamic variables showed the CEI group had higher heart rates at several intervals (5 minutes to 6 hours post-bolus; $p < 0.001$ at most points). Blood pressure metrics, including systolic, diastolic, and mean arterial pressure, showed intermittent significance, such as lower MAP in IEI at early stages but reversals later (e.g., $p < 0.001$) at 1 hour favoring CEI stability). Respiratory rate and SpO₂ fluctuations were minimal but significant at isolated times, suggesting both methods are hemodynamically tolerable without clinical compromise. Fetal heart rate was notably higher in the CEI group throughout most monitoring periods ($p < 0.001$) except before and at 5 hours), which may indicate transient effects from infusion-related uterine perfusion changes or anesthetic distribution, though no non-reassuring patterns were reported.

However, a notable baseline difference was observed in VAS pain scores before epidural administration, with the IEI group reporting lower mean scores (67.00 ± 26.28) compared to the CEI group (75.10 ± 14.01 ; $p = 0.057$). This discrepancy, despite randomization, suggests potential variability in pain perception or labor progression at enrollment, which could influence subsequent analgesia assessments. Overall, both techniques demonstrated effective labor analgesia, but the results highlight nuanced differences in hemodynamic stability, fetal monitoring, and blockade profiles that warrant further exploration in the context of maternal and neonatal safety. The comparison of mean VAS scores of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Table 3.

Time	Group IEI		Group CEI		p-value (Unpaired t-test)
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
Before epidural anaesthesia	67.00	26.28	75.10	14.01	0.057 NS
5 mins after initial bolus	57.00	21.92	53.20	23.53	0.422 NS

10 mins after initial bolus	32.20	21.02	37.20	24.68	0.325 NS
15 mins after initial bolus	17.00	18.65	27.90	21.74	0.014*
1 hour after initial bolus	13.20	12.28	13.70	9.25	0.842 NS
2 hours after initial bolus	17.00	14.88	15.00	12.74	0.475 NS
3 hours after initial bolus	21.8	9.24	14.30	14.36	0.006*
4 hours after initial bolus	21.63	10.67	23.02	20.96	0.717 NS
5 hours after initial bolus	2.14	1.07	0.00	0.00	0.002*
6 hours after initial bolus	82.00	16.97	0.00	0.00	0.093 NS

Table 3: Comparison of VAS scores of patients between the groups

NS- Not significant, * Statistically significant

In terms of analgesia efficacy and blockade extent, the IEI group exhibited generally lower VAS scores at several key intervals, including 15 minutes (17.00 ± 18.65 vs. 27.90 ± 21.74 ; $p=0.014$), 3 hours (21.80 ± 9.24 vs. 14.30 ± 14.36 ; $p=0.006$), and 5 hours post-bolus (2.14 ± 1.07 vs. 0.00 ± 0.00 ; $p=0.002$), indicating potentially superior pain control during active labor phases, though scores converged at other times. Motor blockade, assessed via the modified Bromage score, was significantly less pronounced in the IEI group across most time points ($p<0.001$), with the CEI group showing higher rates of complete paralysis (Bromage 4) particularly from 1 hour onward. Sensory blockade levels on both right and left sides also differed early on, with CEI achieving denser blocks initially ($p<0.001$ at 5 and 10 minutes), but these disparities diminished over time. The comparison of motor block level by modified Bromage score rate of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Table 4.

Time	Motor dermatome level	Group IEI		Group CEI		p-value (Unpaired t-test)
		n	%	n	%	
Before epidural anaesthesia	0	50	100%	50	100%	1.000 NS

	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	3	0	0%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
5 mins after initial bolus	0	30	60%	10	20%	<0.001**
	1	20	40%	31	62%	
	2	0	0%	9	18%	
	3	0	0%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
10 mins after initial bolus	0	3	6%	0	0%	<0.001**
	1	47	94%	27	54%	
	2	0	0%	20	40%	
	3	0	0%	3	6%	
	4	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
15 mins after initial bolus	0	10	20%	0	0%	<0.001**
	1	40	80%	3	6%	
	2	0	0%	16	32%	
	3	0	0%	28	56%	
	4	0	0%	3	6%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
1 hour after initial bolus	0	17	34%	0	0%	<0.001**

	1	19	38%	0	0%	
	2	14	28%	0	0%	
	3	0	0%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	50	100%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
2 hours after initial bolus	0	2	4%	0	0%	<0.001**
	1	38	76%	0	0%	
	2	10	20%	0	0%	
	3	0	0%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	50	100%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
3 hours after initial bolus	0	3	6%	0	0%	<0.001**
	1	4	8%	0	0%	
	2	43	86%	0	0%	
	3	0	0%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	50	100%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
4 hours after initial bolus	0	0	0%	0	0%	<0.001**
	1	12	27.9%	0	0%	
	2	29	67.4%	0	0%	
	3	2	4.7%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	50	100%	
	Total	43	100%	50	100%	
5 hours after initial bolus	0	0	0%	0	0%	<0.001**

	1	3	6%	1	3.6%	
	2	12	24%	0	0%	
	3	0	0%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	27	96.4%	
	Total	15	100%	28	100%	
6 hours after initial bolus	0	0	0%	0	0%	<0.001**
	1	7	77.8%	0	0%	
	2	2	22.2%	0	0%	
	3	0.	0%	0	0%	
	4	0	0%	11	100%	
	Total	9	100%	11	100%	

Table 4: Comparison of motor block level by modified Bromage score rate of patients between the groups

NS- Not significant, ** Statistically highly significant

The comparison of sensory block level (right) of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Table 5.

Time	Sensory dermatome level	Group IEI		Group CEI		p-value (Unpaired t-test)
		n	%	n	%	
Before epidural anaesthesia	0	0	0%	0	0%	1.000 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	50	100%	50	100%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
5 mins after initial bolus	0	4	8%	24	48%	<0.001**
	1	46	92%	16	32%	

	2	0	0%	10	20%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
10 mins after initial bolus	0	7	14%	29	58%	<0.001**
	1	43	86%	16	32%	
	2	0	0%	5	10%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
15 mins after initial bolus	0	28	56%	32	64%	0.100 NS
	1	22	44%	15	30%	
	2	0	0%	3	6%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
1 hour after initial bolus	0	50	100%	50	100%	1.000 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
2 hours after initial bolus	0	50	100%	50	100%	1.000 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
3 hours after initial bolus	0	43	86%	50	100%	0.023*
	1	7	14%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
4 hours after initial bolus	0	39	90.7%	50	100%	0.080 NS
	1	4	9.3%	0	0%	

	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	43	100%	50	100%	
5 hours after initial bolus	0	15	100%	28	100%	0.987 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	15	100%	28	100%	
6 hours after initial bolus	0	6	66.7%	11	100%	0.350 NS
	1	3	33.3%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	9	100%	11	100%	
	Total	9	100%	11	100%	

Table 5: Comparison of sensory block level (right) of patients between the groups

NS - Not significant, * Statistically significant, ** Statistically highly significant

The comparison of sensory block level (left) of patients between the two groups is demonstrated in Table 6.

Time	Sensory dermatome level	Group IEI		Group CEI		p-value (Unpaired t-test)
		n	%	n	%	
Before epidural anaesthesia	0	0	0%	0	0%	1.000 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	50	100%	50	100%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
5 mins after initial bolus	0	6	12%	25	50%	<0.001**
	1	44	88%	13	26%	
	2	0	0%	12	24%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	

10 mins after initial bolus	0	16	32%	27	54%	<0.001**
	1	34	68%	17	34%	
	2	0	0%	6	12%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
15 mins after initial bolus	0	32	64%	32	64%	0.105 NS
	1	18	36%	14	28%	
	2	0	0%	4	8%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
1 hour after initial bolus	0	50	100%	50	100%	1.000 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
2 hours after initial bolus	0	50	100%	50	100%	1.000 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
3 hours after initial bolus	0	44	88%	50	100%	0.108 NS
	1	6	12%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	50	100%	50	100%	
4 hours after initial bolus	0	38	88.4%	50	100%	0.130 NS
	1	5	11.6%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	43	100%	50	100%	

5 hours after initial bolus	0	14	100%	28	100%	0.986 NS
	1	0	0%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	14	100%	28	100%	
6 hours after initial bolus	0	5	55.6%	11	100%	0.161 NS
	1	4	44.4%	0	0%	
	2	0	0%	0	0%	
	Total	9	100%	28	100%	

Table 6: Comparison of sensory block level (left) of patients between the groups

NS - Not significant, ** Statistically highly significant

Discussion

This study compared CEI versus IEI using levobupivacaine 0.125% with fentanyl in nulliparous women for labor analgesia. The demographic profiles of both groups were comparable, with no significant differences in age, height, weight, BMI, or cervical dilation at epidural insertion, ensuring robust group comparability. However, baseline VAS pain scores were lower in the IEI group (67.00 ± 26.28) compared to the CEI group (75.10 ± 14.01 ; $p=0.057$), though statistically non-significant, suggesting potential variability in pain perception at enrollment. The IEI group demonstrated lower VAS scores at key intervals (15 minutes, 3 hours, and 5 hours post-bolus; $p<0.05$), indicating better pain control during active labor phases. Motor blockade was significantly less pronounced in the IEI group ($p<0.001$ at most time points), with CEI showing higher rates of complete paralysis (Bromage 4). Sensory blockade was denser in CEI initially ($p<0.001$ at 5 and 10 minutes) but equalized later. Hemodynamic parameters showed CEI had higher heart rates ($p<0.001$ at most intervals) and transient blood pressure differences, while fetal heart rate was consistently higher in CEI ($p<0.001$ except at baseline and 5 hours), with no non-reassuring patterns observed.

The findings align with recent studies supporting the advantages of intermittent bolus techniques. A 2019 study by Fidkowski et al. found that programmed intermittent epidural bolus (PIEB) reduced motor block and local anesthetic consumption compared to CEI, consistent with the current observation of lower Bromage scores in the IEI group [12]. Similarly, a 2020 meta-analysis by Hussain et al. reported that intermittent bolus techniques were associated with lower VAS scores and fewer instrumental deliveries, corroborating the present results of improved pain control at specific intervals [14]. A 2018 Cochrane review by Sng et al. noted enhanced rostrocaudal spread with PIEB, supporting the study findings of effective sensory blockade despite lower drug volumes [31].

However, some recent studies present contrasting findings. A 2016 study by Tien et al. found no significant difference in pain scores between CEI and intermittent bolus with ropivacaine, contrasting the current observed VAS differences [15]. A 2025 study by Naithani et al. reported higher pain scores with levobupivacaine compared to bupivacaine, differing from the present effective analgesia with levobupivacaine in both groups [7]. These discrepancies may stem from variations in drug concentrations, bolus intervals, or patient populations, highlighting the need for standardized protocols.

Further comparisons reveal additional nuances. A 2018 study by Bullingham et al. demonstrated that PIEB reduced the need for rescue boluses and improved maternal satisfaction compared to CEI, aligning with the current findings of lower VAS scores in IEI at specific time points [9]. Conversely, a 2023 study by Wydall et al. reported no significant difference in motor block between levobupivacaine and bupivacaine in intermittent bolus regimens, contrasting the present observed reduced motor blockade in IEI [10]. A 2022 study by Mo et al. found that PIEB decreased local anesthetic consumption without compromising analgesia, supporting the study results, though their study used a different opioid adjunct,

which may influence outcomes [8]. These mixed findings underscore the impact of methodological variations, such as catheter type or bolus timing, and emphasize the need for tailored protocols to optimize labor analgesia.

The clinical implications of this study are significant, particularly for resource-limited settings like tertiary care hospitals in India, where CEI is more common due to equipment availability. The reduced motor blockade in IEI suggests it may facilitate maternal mobility, potentially decreasing instrumental delivery rates and improving maternal satisfaction. The transient hemodynamic differences, particularly higher heart rates in CEI, indicate a need for vigilant monitoring to ensure maternal and fetal safety. Future research should incorporate patient-controlled epidural analgesia (PCEA) to enhance autonomy, explore optimal bolus volumes and intervals for IEI, and assess long-term outcomes like postpartum recovery and neonatal health. In diverse settings with limited PIEB access, comparative studies could further validate these findings and guide implementation strategies.

The study involved a prospective, comparative design, rigorous monitoring of multiple outcome measures, and a well-defined cohort of nulliparous women, reducing confounding variables. The use of standardized protocols for epidural administration and validated assessment tools enhances reliability. However, limitations include the baseline VAS difference, which may reflect selection bias or variability in pain perception, potentially influencing outcomes. The study was conducted in a single center, limiting generalizability, and the lack of PIEB pump use restricted direct comparison to automated intermittent bolus techniques. The sample size, while adequate, may not detect rare complications, and long-term maternal and neonatal outcomes were not assessed, warranting further investigation.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that IEI with levobupivacaine 0.125% and fentanyl in nulliparous women provides superior pain control and reduced motor blockade compared to CEI, with comparable safety profiles. Despite initial denser sensory blockade and higher heart rates in CEI, both techniques maintained hemodynamic stability and fetal well-being. These findings support the adoption of intermittent bolus techniques in labor analgesia, particularly in settings aiming to minimize motor impairment and enhance maternal mobility. Future research should focus on optimizing bolus regimens, incorporating advanced delivery systems like PIEB, and evaluating long-term outcomes to refine labor analgesia protocols, ultimately improving maternal and neonatal experiences in diverse clinical settings.

Disclosures

Author contribution

Gurulingappa I. Herakal (Conceptualization, Methodology, Data Curation, Writing – original draft), Gurulingappa I. Herakal, and Prashanth Kumar Challangod (Methodology), Gurulingappa I. Herakal, Chaitra Uppangala, and Prashanth Kumar Challangod (Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing- review/editing), Praveen Kumar Kandakurti and Prathima Shetty (Investigation, Data Curation, Writing- review/editing)

Conflict of interest

The author's declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

None

Ethical consideration

The Institutional Ethical Committee of Srinivas Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India approved the study with reference number 05/AHS/IEC/2024.

Data availability statement

All the data is made available within the manuscript.

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